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Photo Courtesy of HITT Contracting

Insights on Expanding the Role of Structural Composites in Construction

ICCM 24 – RR/1

Acknowledge Where “Impacts” Matter

Typical Medium Scale Ultra-Low Energy Residential Building

Source: The Institution of Structural Engineers – *How to Calculate Embodied Carbon*, 2020

Practice Competitive Sustainability

Exterior Building Wall Technology is Evolving

State of the Art	Precast Concrete Wall Panels	FRP Response
<i>Insulated Sandwich Structures</i>	Typical PIC: structural wythe / polystyrene insulation / exterior architectural wythe	We've Got This
<i>Smart Assemblies</i>	Embedded sensors on IoT platform for real time monitoring of temps, RH, strains	Mostly Translates
<i>Digital Fabrication</i>	Rapid prototyping of custom frameworks to create complex architectural features	Translates
<i>Sustainable Materials</i>	Standard supplements include fly ash, slag, silica fume and even carbon capture tech	Adopt Circularity
<i>BIM and Digital Twins</i>	Facilitates clash detection, scheduling, logistics and life cycle performance tracking	Required
<i>Design Standards</i>	PCI Design Handbook defines fire, seismic, connection design and build procedures	ASTM, NFPA ACMA
<i>Construction Logistics</i>	Just in time panelized construction, self aligning connections, integrated lift systems	Translates

Stay Focused on Reducing Product Weight

Wall Panel	Outer Wall	Core	Inner Wall	Areal Mass (#/sq ft)	Typ Dims (sq ft)	Panel Mass (#)	Mass Factor
High Density PIC 150 #/cu ft	3" Wythe	3-5" PS	6" Wythe	112	300	33,600	> 6 x
Low Density PIC 110#/cu ft	3" Wythe	3-5" PS	6" Wythe	83	300	24,900	~ 5 x
Typical FRP Sandwich Panel	0.5" FRP	2-12" PISO	0.5" FRP	17	300	5,100	x

The **Extra Mass** of a Building's Foundation and Steel Framing required to support a heavier Envelope materially impacts:

Project Delivery Time, Cost and Carbon Footprint

Coupon Level Testing for Design Data

Determined by Nuances of Fabric Reinforcement

Single Ply of Heavy Quad-Axial Fabric

Asymmetric & Anisotropic

Typical Response to Reduced Temperature

Double Ply of Heavy Quad-Axial Fabric Symmetric & Orthotropic

$$[B] = 0$$

$$\epsilon^{Th}_{(x)} \neq \epsilon^{Th}_{(y)}$$

Typical Response to Reduced Temperature

Double Ply of Heavy Quad-Axial Fabric

Asymmetric & Quasi-Isotropic

[B] ≠ 0

Typical Response to Reduced Temperature

Quad Ply of Heavy Quad-Axial Fabric

Symmetric & Quasi-Isotropic

Typical Response to Reduced Temperature

Standard CTE Test Method Options

<i>Method</i>	TMA ASTM E831	Dilatometry ASTM D228	Optical Comparator ISO 11359-2	Strain Gauges ASTM D5335
Typical Materials	Polymers Thin Films	Bulk Materials Composites	Metals, Polymers Composites	Rocks Composites
Temp Range	-120°C to 900°C	-180°C to 900°C	-50°C to 300°C	20°C to 260°C
Sample Width	Up to 10 mm	Std 12.7 mm	10 to 50 mm	Gauge Dependent
Direction	Uniaxial	Uniaxial	Full Field	Gauge Alignment
Surface Prep	Smooth & Flat Parallel Ends	Smooth & Flat Parallel Ends	Clear Speckling Good Lighting	Flat Bondable Surface
Equipment Cost	\$50 to \$100K	\$60 to \$120K	\$80 to \$250K	\$10 to \$30K

Determining In-Plane CTE Per ASTM D5335

Photo Courtesy of UDRI, Dayton, OH

Reference Gauge
on Standard Panel
Occupies $\frac{1}{4}$ of
Wheatstone
Bridge

Separate Circuits
Constructed for
the Upper and
Lower Faces

Assembly Testing of Exterior Wall Panels

Photo Courtesy of HITT Contracting

- Air Penetration
- Water Penetration
- Sound Transfer
- Heat Transfer
- Smoke Evolution
- Flame Spread
- Environmental

A Very Early NFPA 285 Test Specimen

TC Location Schematic

Unitary Sandwich Panel

NFPA 285 – A Sequence of Intensifying Fluxes

**Room Burner
is Activated**

**Window Burner
Is Activated**

**Combined Burners
Ramp Up Heat**

Stage	1	2	3	4	5	6
Time (min)	0 - 5	5 - 10	10 - 15	15 - 20	20 - 25	25 - 30
Room Gas (CFM)	35.50	35.50	43.75	43.58	43.58	47.37
Window Gas (CFM)	0.00	4.30	5.60	8.10	11.00	15.60

Understand the Intent of Standards

A Unitary Wall Panel is Not Anticipated by NFPA 285

Horizontal and Vertical Joints are Required in the Fire Zone

Revised NFPA 285 Wall Assembly Specimen

Places Panel Edges, Specified Sealant & Backer Rod in Fire Zone

Combining Reductive & ADM on 3/2 CNC Offers Architectural Freedom w/Inflexible Schedules

Rough Cut Foam Backer

Coat Shaped Foam w/ Paste

Combining Reductive & ADM on 3/2 CNC

Requires BIM / REVIT / CAD / FEA / CAM Inter-Operability

Cure Paste Coating Layer

Rough & Final Finish Plug/Tool

It's Costly Not to Manage Waste Streams

Pragmatic Circularity

Create Clean Streams

Options to Re-Use Closed Cell Foam Scrap

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Questions ?

